

The Role of Incentives in Enhancing Employee Satisfaction: A Comprehensive Analysis

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The Researchers

DEDICATION

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ABSTRACT

Employee satisfaction plays a very important role in the success of an organization because it influences the success, productivity, engagement and retention Locke (1969). This study investigates the role of incentives both monetary and non-monetary in enhancing employee satisfaction within various organizational settings. By examining and reviewing the available and existing literature and conducting a comprehensive analysis through surveys, questionnaires and interviews with employees across different sectors primarily in Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, the study aims to determine which kind or types of incentives are most effective and ideal to use in most organizations in boosting their employee's motivation and satisfaction. The research also explores the potential gap between the organization's management perception of effective incentives and the actual needs of its employees. The findings from this study will provide valuable insights for those organizations seeking help on how they will optimize their incentive programs that will improve their employee satisfaction, retention, and overall organizational performance.

Keywords:- Employee Satisfaction; Incentives; Motivation; Non-Monetary Incentives; Rewards and Recognition.

CHAPTER ONE

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

A. Introduction

Employee satisfaction has long been recognized as a critical factor and component influencing individual performance and organizations' overall success and sustainability. High levels of job satisfaction are associated with increased productivity, improved workplace morale, higher employee retention, and better organizational performance.

In today's competitive business world, organizations continuously seek more effective strategies to keep their employees engaged, motivated, and satisfied. One dominant strategy involves monetary strategies, such as salary increases and bonuses, and non-monetary strategies, which include recognition, professional development, opportunities, and flexible work arrangements.

Incentives are designed to motivate and satisfy employees by rewarding their positive behaviors and good performance. However, the relationship between these incentives and employee satisfaction may vary based on different factors, including but not limited to individual employee preferences, the organization's environment or culture, and the type of industry the organization has belonged to. While many organizations promote incentive programs, they often struggle with whether these incentives effectively meet the employees' expectations and will foster long-term job satisfaction.

This comprehensive analysis aims to explore the role of incentives in enhancing employee satisfaction within the context of Cabanatuan City. The study's researchers will examine various incentive programs and strategies, their effectiveness, and regional organizations' challenges. By studying relevant theories and previous data, this study seeks to provide insights and recommendations for businesses looking to improve in satisfying their employees through well-designed incentive programs. Ultimately, this analysis will point out the vital connection between employee satisfaction and the overall success of organizations in Cabanatuan City, focusing on developing a more proactive approach to workplace motivation.

B. Review of Related Literature and Studies

The relationship between incentives and employee satisfaction and motivation has been widely studied in organizational behavior, with various theories and frameworks developed to explain how such incentives affect work performance and job satisfaction. This part of the study reviews the key related literature and previous studies about the role of incentives in enhancing employee satisfaction, mainly focusing on the unique socioeconomic landscape of Cabanatuan City.

Several motivational theories will help us understand the role of incentives in employee satisfaction. Among the most notable is Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), which suggests that individuals are motivated by a series of hierarchical needs that start from physiological needs until the highest peak, self-actualization. He said that in an organization, incentives such as salary increases, promotions, and recognitions often address the needs of its employees, leading to improved performance and satisfaction. Another critical theory is Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959), which states the difference between the hygiene factors (salary, job security) that are said to be preventing dissatisfaction and motivators (recognition, achievements) that actively affect and enhance job satisfaction. Herzberg's Model emphasizes that monetary incentives alone may or may not be sufficient to increase employee satisfaction; instead, employees may also require non-monetary incentives like professional development and career growth opportunities.

Self Determination Theory (SDT) by Deci & Ryan, 1985 also highlights the importance of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation arises from internal satisfaction, such as personal growth, while extrinsic motivation arises from external rewards, such as bonuses or promotions. It suggested that while extrinsic rewards can enhance short-term motivation, long-term motivation is still the best, resulting from intrinsic motivators. Monetary incentives have been traditionally viewed as one of the best ways to improve employee satisfaction as this is vital for every human being to use in their everyday lives.

Jenkins, Mitra, Gupta, and Shaw (1998) show that financial rewards, like bonuses, salary increases, and profit sharing, are some of the most used incentives that correlate with employee performance and satisfaction. However, their study also stated that monetary rewards may lose their motivational power if considered entitlement rather than performance-based.

Furthermore, non-monetary incentives have also gained popularity as organizations prioritize having a more engaged and satisfied workforce.

Torrington, Hall, and Taylor (2008) emphasize the growing importance of non-monetary rewards, which include flexible work arrangements, professional development, and recognition by management to enhance employee satisfaction. Armstrong and Brown (2006) agreed with this theory and also stated that employees often value recognition, autonomy, and opportunities that will develop and enhance their careers rather than financial rewards. They said that non-monetary incentives are particularly more effective in fostering long-term engagement by employees by addressing their accomplishments.

On the other hand, Tremblay, Sire, and Balkin (2000) highlighted the need for organizations to customize their incentive programs based on the needs of their workforce. Their research suggests that a “one-size-fits-all” incentive approach to employees is ineffective, as employees in the organizations have different age groups, roles, and levels of expertise.

Kinicki and Kreitner (2003) stated that when employees' sincere needs and supplications are not considered and managed adequately, displeasure, discontent, and pilfering prevail, facilitating an unattractive state of mind toward work.

Rothwell and Kazanas (2004) discovered that organizational effectiveness becomes vague when employees feel displeased, disgruntled, or discouraged about how things are done. Several factors have been identified to influence high job satisfaction in the workplace: career development and progression, opportunities for growth, communication, training, and other work-related issues (Bennett & Minty, 2005).

Burgess, Simon, and Ratto Marisa (2003) stated that employees feel satisfied only when they derive pleasure from their job. This feeling influences their attitude to work, which eventually leads to more excellent performance. Studies indicated various dynamic ways of motivating workers for efficiency and effectiveness: pay, interpersonal relationship, sense of achievement, etc. (Salau et al., 2014)”. In business, the relationship between incentives and job satisfaction cannot be undervalued; the two variables depend on each other but respond differently to increased employee engagement, participation and retention, competence, commitment, and involvement.

Locke's (1976) Range of Affect Theory stated that employee satisfaction is significantly affected by the discrepancy between what employees expect from their jobs and what they receive (Lock, 1976). This framework identifies the importance of incentives, as they help bridge the gap between expectations and realities.

Several studies indicated a strong correlation between incentives and employee performance. A meta-analysis by Boxall and Macky (2009) revealed that employers who invest in comprehensive incentive programs see higher employee satisfaction and enhanced levels of performance and productivity for their employees. Moreover, in the service sector context, Ramlall (2004) found that recognition programs improve employee commitment and job satisfaction.

Cultural factors also play a crucial role in how most employees perceive and react to various incentives. In the Philippines, where collectivist values are prominent, employees may place greater importance on team-based rewards and recognition than on individualistic systems (Hofstede, 1980). Understanding the local culture of Cabanatuan City can help businesses tailor their incentive strategies effectively.

De Leon and Reyes's (2015) study highlighted that recognition from peers and leaders can significantly enhance employee motivation in Filipino work environments.

While incentive programs can provide numerous benefits, challenges still exist in their implementation. Organizations often face issues such as budget shortages, incentive program design, and never-ending changes in employee expectations. (Kuvaas et al., 2017). For instance, a study conducted in Metro Manila indicates that many small and medium enterprises struggle to design effective incentive programs due to limited resources (Bernal & Salgado, 2019). This emphasizes companies' need to be more strategic and resourceful in designing and implementing their incentive programs, especially in Cabanatuan City.

Several local studies explored the dynamics of employee satisfaction and incentives within specific industries in Cabanatuan City. One example is the research by Santos (2021), who examined the effects of various incentive structures within local manufacturing firms and found that monetary bonuses led to increased job satisfaction. However, recognizing employee contributions through non-monetary means was equally impactful. Additionally, a survey conducted in Cabanatuan's growing BPO sector indicated that flexible work arrangements and traditional incentives were vital to employee satisfaction (Alvarez, 2002).

C. Theoretical or Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this research is based on the relationship between incentives and employee satisfaction, which focuses on monetary and non-monetary incentives as critical variables. The framework the researchers used for this study illustrates how different types of incentives influence employee engagement and motivation, ultimately leading to job satisfaction.

Fig 1: Diagram of the Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the cause-and-effect relationship between incentives and employee satisfaction while considering the influence of other variables, such as the demographics of the employees, organizational culture, and the industry type to which the organization belongs.

D. The Research Problem

Employee Satisfaction is an essential factor in determining an organization's overall success. It directly influences productivity, retention, and overall workplace morale. Considering the implementation of various incentive programs that aim to boost employee motivation and satisfaction, many businesses and organizations are still struggling to determine which type of incentives are best for their employees and the impact on the whole organization. This study seeks to address the gap by assessing the role of monetary and non-monetary incentives in enhancing employee satisfaction. Specifically, it explores how different types of incentives influence employee motivation, productivity, commitment, and overall job satisfaction. It aims to identify which incentives are most effective and ideal in creating a more positive workplace environment.

This study aims to describe the role of incentives in enhancing employee satisfaction. Precisely, it will aim to:

➤ Describe Employees in Terms of:

- Name (Optional)
- Age
- Gender
- Position in the company
- Number of months employed

➤ The Role of Incentives such as:

- Bonuses
- Recognition
- Rewards

➤ *How do these Incentives Impact Employee Engagement in Terms of:*

- Employee engagement in their jobs
- Job Satisfaction
- Commitment to the organization

➤ *What Role do these Incentives Play in:*

- Reducing employee turnover
- Retention of Employees

By investigating these issues, this study seeks to provide insights that can help management develop effective strategies to enhance employee satisfaction during peak seasons, ultimately benefiting both employees and the organization.

E. Hypotheses

- Monetary incentives, such as bonuses and salary increases, significantly affect employee satisfaction compared to non-monetary incentives, such as recognition or rewards.
- Employees who often received performance-based incentives had higher job satisfaction than fixed salaries without performance incentives.
- Flexible work incentives, such as remote work setup or flexible working hours, are associated with higher employee satisfaction than fixed work schedules.
- The availability of career development incentives such as training and promotions positively impacts overall employee satisfaction within the organization.
- Employees who perceive incentives as fair and equitable will report higher job satisfaction than those who perceive incentives as unfair.
- There is a positive relationship between the persistence of incentives provided and overall employee satisfaction levels in an organization.
- Organizations with incentive programs exhibit higher employee satisfaction and team cohesion than organizations without incentive programs.

F. Scope, Delimitation, and Limitations

The study will focus on how several incentive programs affect employees' satisfaction in a selected organization within Cabanatuan City. It thus covers monetary and non-monetary incentives, such as bonuses, schemes of profit-sharing benefits, recognition programs, awards, and so forth. The sample period for the research runs between 2022 and 2024 and will cut across all ranges of employees, from entry staff to middle and upper management. Of particular interest are variables on employee satisfaction, engagement, turnover rates, and perceived effectiveness of offered incentives. Conclusion In the scope, only Cabanatuan City would be involved because participants will be streamed from different industries, giving an overall understanding of the incentive programs within that specific geographic area.

The study will be delimited to organizations within Cabanatuan City, excluding companies from other regions or cities to maintain a localized focus. It will specifically investigate formal incentive programs, such as bonuses, promotions, and employee benefits. It will not consider other factors like workplace culture, leadership styles, or external economic conditions that might also influence employee satisfaction. Additionally, the study will target selected industries, potentially excluding smaller businesses that do not have well-structured incentive systems. Data collection will be limited to employees, excluding other stakeholders such as managers or external evaluators, and will focus solely on the employee perspective.

This study has several limitations; first, the outcome may not be generalized beyond the context of Cabanatuan City because the data will be geographically confined. Secondly, the sample size may be limited by the willingness of organizations to participate. Thus, it may affect the depth and representativeness of the study. This study relies on data obtained through employee self-reporting methods. Thus, it may suffer from biased or inaccurate data due to subjective perceptions. Secondly, the time required to include longitudinal analyses may be limited. Lastly, the organizations within Cabanatuan City may not all have structured incentive programs. This reduces the scope of comparison between different incentive models.

G. Significance of the Study

➤ *The Significance of Studying the Role of Incentives in Enhancing Employee Satisfaction:*

- **For the Researchers:** The researchers can add to the existing related literature on employee motivations and satisfaction. The findings may provide new insights, confirm existing theories, and help deepen academic understanding of the relationship between incentives and employee satisfaction.

By investigating this topic, the researchers can somehow bridge the gap between the available theories and their actual practice. Their work can provide recommendations for organizations seeking to improve their incentive programs that target employee satisfaction.

- **For Organizations:** This study can provide valuable insights into how various types of incentives (monetary and non-monetary programs) influence employee motivation and satisfaction. This understanding can help organizations tailor or design incentive programs to effectively engage and motivate their workforce.

By identifying the relationship between incentives and employee satisfaction, the research study could suggest that happier employees are more likely to increase their productivity, lower turnover rates, and higher overall performance. The study can explore how incentives can contribute to a more positive workplace culture that promotes employee well-being and satisfaction, leading to better teamwork, collaboration, and organizational commitment. Findings from this research study can transform HR policies and practices. Managers, Supervisors, and leaders can use the information provided by the researchers to design incentive programs that are aligned with the current needs and expectations of their employees to foster a more engaged and satisfied workforce.

- **For the Society:** By improving employee satisfaction, organizations can contribute to society's overall well-being. Satisfied employees are more likely to experience better work-life balance, which can affect and enhance their overall quality of life and ultimately positively impact their communities.
- **For Future Researchers:** The study's outcome may serve as the basis for follow-up research on other incentive programs that can motivate and satisfy employees.

In summary, studying the role of incentives in enhancing employee satisfaction is significant because it can contribute valuable knowledge and practical recommendations that benefit employees, organizations, and society.

H. Definition of Terms

These definitions provide a foundational understanding of the critical concepts related to incentives and employee satisfaction, helping facilitate deeper discussion and analysis of the study.

- **Descriptive Research:** is a research method used to try and determine the characteristics of a population or phenomenon. Using descriptive research, you can identify patterns in the characteristics of a group to essentially establish everything you need to understand apart from why something has happened
- **Employee Engagement** refers to an employee's level of commitment and involvement in the organization. Engaged employees are typically more productive and satisfied when performing their duties and responsibilities.
- **Employee Satisfaction:** measures how content employees are with their jobs, work environment, responsibilities, management support, salary, and career growth opportunities.
- **Incentives:** Rewards or benefits designed to motivate employees to perform their jobs at a higher level.
- **Job Performance:** refers to the degree to which an employee successfully fulfills their job responsibilities and contributes to the goal of the whole organization. Performance can be evaluated based on productivity, quality of work, and overall effectiveness of their role in the organization.
- **Mixed- Method Approach:** A mixed methods approach is a research method that combines qualitative and quantitative research methods in a single study. The goal is to use the strengths of each data type to gain a more comprehensive understanding of a research topic.
- **Monetary Incentives:** are financial rewards given to employees by management, such as bonuses, commissions, salary increases, or profit-sharing arrangements.
- **Motivation:** refers to the inner drive of employees that enables them to act toward achieving their specific goals. Workplace motivation can come from various sources, including incentives, recognition, and personal aspirations.
- **Non-monetary Incentives:** are non-financial rewards that motivate employees, such as recognition, promotions, awards, career development opportunities, or work-life balance measures.

- **Qualitative Method:** is a method of inquiry that involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data to understand human behavior and social realities
- **Quantitative Method:** is a method of research that involves collecting and analyzing numerical data to understand, describe, and predict a phenomenon.
- **Organizational Culture:** refers to the shared values, beliefs, and practices that shape the social and psychological environment of the organization. A positive organizational culture can significantly impact employee satisfaction.
- **Population:** is the entire group of people, objects, or events that a researcher is interested in studying. The population is defined by the research's objectives and the specific attributes or parameters being investigated.
- **Respondents:** there are persons who answers questions in a survey or interview.
- **Retention Rate:** refers to the percentage of employees who remain with an organization over a certain period. High retention rates often indicate more satisfied employees within an organization.
- **Society:** is a structured community of individuals who share common values, customs, and institutions.
- **Work Environment:** refers to the environment in which an employee works. This includes physical, social, and organizational factors. A positive work environment can enhance employee satisfaction and productivity.

CHAPTER TWO METHODS AND PROCEDURES

A. Research Design

The researchers used a descriptive research design, utilizing a mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques.

B. Locale of the Study

Fig 2: Map of Cabanatuan City

(The 2.4×4.0 km study area in Cabanatuan containing the “city center” (Poblacion, highlighted). Base map derived from satellite imagery (Google Earth Pro, 2015, 2016). Additional data from OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2016).

Cabanatuan, a city located in the province of Nueva Ecija, Philippines, serves as the locale for this study due to its active economic growth and diverse industries. Known as the "Agricultural Capital of the Philippines," Cabanatuan has seen rapid urbanization and expansion in recent years, making it an ideal setting for studying employee satisfaction and the role of incentive programs. The city's economy is driven by various sectors, including agriculture, manufacturing, retail, education, healthcare, and information technology (IT), offering an abundant and various sector of industries to explore the impact of incentives on employee satisfaction.

As the center of Nueva Ecija, Cabanatuan City is home to a growing number of businesses, from large enterprises to small and medium-sized companies. This diverse economic landscape presents an opportunity to study a wide range of incentive programs across different industries and job levels. Moreover, the city's strategic location, proximity to other urban areas, and robust infrastructure make it an important player in the regional economy, providing a unique perspective on how incentive strategies are implemented and their effectiveness in various organizational settings.

Cabanatuan's varied industries and demographic characteristics allow the researchers to conduct a comprehensive examination of employee satisfaction in different contexts, such as job roles, years of experience, and company culture. By focusing on Cabanatuan City, this study aims to provide insights into the specific challenges faced by businesses in the region and to offer practical recommendations for improving employee satisfaction through effective incentive programs. The findings from this study will be particularly valuable to local employers, policymakers, and business leaders seeking to enhance employee engagement and foster long-term organizational success within the city's rapidly evolving business environment.

C. Descriptive Research Design

The study is descriptive because the researchers gathered detailed information about the types of incentives provided by organizations in Cabanatuan City and how employees see these incentives. This design will help describe and analyze organizations' current incentive practices and their effect on employees and ultimately identify patterns and relationships between incentives and employee satisfaction.

D. Mixed-Methods Approach

The researchers integrate quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide readers with a complete understanding of the study under investigation.

- **Quantitative Method:** The research study involves a structured survey distributed to a sample of employees through (Google Forms). The survey/questionnaires use Likert-scale questions to help researchers quantify employee satisfaction and perceptions of monetary and non-monetary incentives. This provides the researchers with statistical data that can be analyzed to identify the incentives that most employees seek from their organizations.
- **Qualitative Method:** To supplement the survey data, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a smaller group of employees. This will allow the researchers to explore employees' attitudes toward their organizations' incentive programs deeply. This will help the study capture the complexity of employee motivations and preferences that the quantitative data might not fully represent.

E. Population and Sampling

This study's population consists of employees from various industries in Cabanatuan City, including, but not limited to, manufacturing, services, information technology (IT), healthcare, education, and retailing. The study focuses on full-time employees who usually receive incentives across different hierarchical levels (entry-level, mid-level, senior-level, and executive positions). The study also targets employees with at least one year of work experience in their current organization to ensure sufficient exposure to the incentive programs.

The researchers for this study aim to gather data from a sample of fifty (50) employees for the quantitative survey and at least 20 employees for the qualitative interviews. The larger sample allows the researchers to state significant results statistically, while the smaller sample provides in-depth insights into the study they are investigating.

The researchers used the stratified random sampling technique to select participants for their quantitative survey to ensure proper representation across different industries, job levels, and demographic factors. After the researchers divided the population into strata (by industry, job levels, and demographics), a random selection of employees from each group was chosen to complete the survey. This ensured a balanced representation and enhanced the reliability of the study's findings.

On the other hand, the researchers used the Purposive Sampling Method for the qualitative interviews, which focused on employees who have specific or relevant experiences with organizations' incentive systems. The researchers selected employees from various industries and positions to ensure reliable outcomes.

F. Respondents of the Study/ Participants/ Subject

The respondents of this study will consist of fifty (50) full-time employees who will be drawn from various industries, job levels, and demographic backgrounds in Cabanatuan City, which will contribute to the quantitative survey area of the study and twenty (20) employees with more experience in the incentive programs of different organizations which the researchers will be conducting in-depth interviews that ultimately will complete the qualitative area of the study. Their inputs are essential for understanding the impact of incentives on employee satisfaction.

G. Characteristics of the Respondents:

The respondents of this study will include respondents from a wide range of sectors in Cabanatuan City to ensure diverse representation. These sectors will be composed of employees from Manufacturing, Service Industry (such as hospitality and retail), Information Technology (IT), Healthcare, Education, Finance, and other relevant industries. Respondents will be selected from various job levels, including entry-level employees, mid-level employees, senior-level employees, as well as management and executive positions. To further enhance the diversity of the sample, demographic factors such as age, gender, and years of experience will be considered. Participants will be grouped into age categories (e.g., 18-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-55, 56 and above), with all genders being included to ensure inclusivity. Additionally, the length of service of the employees will be categorized into ranges (e.g., 1-3 years, 4-6 years, 7-10 years, and more than 10 years) to capture the perspectives of individuals with varying levels of experience in the workforce.

Potential respondents will be contacted through their respective organizations via e-mail, messenger, internal communication channels, or as wished by the researchers. The researchers will inform about their study, including its purpose and significance. To encourage participation, they will ensure all the respondents the utmost confidentiality of the information they provide.

H. Research Instruments

A mix of quantitative and qualitative research instruments will be employed to gather comprehensive data from employees and organizations in Cabanatuan City. The following research instruments will be used:

➤ Survey Questionnaire

The primary instrument for data collection will be a structured survey questionnaire via Google Forms, designed to measure employees' perceptions of incentives and their impact on job satisfaction. The survey will include a variety of question formats, such as

- **Multiple-choice questions** to identify the types of incentives (e.g., monetary rewards, benefits, recognition) offered and preferred by employees.
- **Open-ended questions** allow employees to provide additional feedback on how incentives influence their satisfaction and performance.

➤ Likert Scale Questions

A series of statements and questions will be presented to measure employees' levels of agreement or disagreement on a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Very Important). These questions will focus on various aspects of incentive programs within the workplace. Areas of assessment will include employees' satisfaction with current incentive programs, their perceptions of the fairness and adequacy of these incentives, and the overall impact of incentives on motivation, performance, and job satisfaction. Additionally, the survey will explore the importance of non-monetary incentives, such as recognition and career development opportunities, in fostering a positive work environment.

- **Questionnaire:** Role and Impact of Incentives on Employee Satisfaction in Cabanatuan City

This questionnaire is designed to assess the role and impact of incentives on employee satisfaction in the various sectors of Cabanatuan City. Your honest responses will greatly help and contribute to the success of this study. All information provided will be handle with utmost discretion and will be kept confidential and will only be use for the purpose of the study.

➤ Instructions:

Please put a check mark on your chosen answer.

➤ Section 1: Demographic Information

- Age
 - ✓ 18-25
 - ✓ 26-35
 - ✓ 36-45
 - ✓ 46-55
 - ✓ 56 and above
- Gender
 - ✓ Male
 - ✓ Female
 - ✓ Other
- Job Position:
 - ✓ Entry-level
 - ✓ Mid-level
 - ✓ Senior-level
 - ✓ Managerial Level
 - ✓ Executive

- *Years of Experience in the Organization:*

- ✓ Less than 1 year
- ✓ 1-3 years
- ✓ 4-6 years
- ✓ 7-10 years
- ✓ More than 10 years

- *Industry Sector:*

- ✓ Manufacturing
- ✓ Retailing
- ✓ Services
- ✓ IT/Tech
- ✓ Education
- ✓ Healthcare
- ✓ Other (Please specify)
- ✓ _____

➤ *Section 2: Incentive Programs in your organization*

- *Does your Organization Offer Any Form of Incentives?*

- ✓ Yes
- ✓ No
- ✓ If yes, what types of incentives are provided? (Select all that apply)
- ✓ Performance-based bonuses
- ✓ Profit- sharing
- ✓ Recognition programs (Employee of the Month, etc.)
- ✓ Flexible work hours
- ✓ Extra Paid time- off
- ✓ Professional development opportunities (training, workshops, etc.)
- ✓ Promotions or career advancement opportunities
- ✓ Non-monetary rewards (gifts, vouchers, etc.)
- ✓ Other (please specify if possible)
- ✓ _____

- *Which type of Incentive Motivates you the Most?*

- ✓ Monetary (bonuses, salary increases)
- ✓ Non-monetary (recognition, career growth opportunities, etc.)
- ✓ Both equally

➤ *Section 3. Perceived Impact of Incentives on Job Satisfaction*

- *To what Extent do Monetary Incentives Influence your Overall Job Satisfaction?*

- ✓ 1: No Influence
- ✓ 2: Little Influence
- ✓ 3: Some Influence
- ✓ 4: Moderate Influence
- ✓ 5: Strong Influence

- *To What Extent do Non-Monetary Incentives Influence your Overall Job Satisfaction?*

- 1: No Influence
- 2: Little Influence
- 3: Some Influence
- 4: Moderate Influence
- 5: Strong Influence

- *Which Type of Incentive do you Value More in your Current Role?*

- ✓ Monetary Incentives
- ✓ Non- monetary Incentives
- ✓ Both Equally

- *How Important are Incentives in Keeping you Motivated and Satisfied in your Job?*

- ✓ 1: Not Important
- ✓ 2: Slightly Important
- ✓ 3: Moderately Important
- ✓ 4: Important
- ✓ 5: Very Important

- *What is the Most Effective Incentive you Have Received? (Open-Ended)*

✓ _____

➤ *Section 4: Job Satisfaction*

- *Overall, how Satisfied are you with your Job?*

- ✓ 1: Very Dissatisfied
- ✓ 2: Dissatisfied
- ✓ 3: Neutral
- ✓ 4: Satisfied
- ✓ 5: Very Satisfied

- *Do you Believe that the Incentives Provided by your Organization Align with your Personal and Professional Goals?*

- ✓ Yes
- ✓ No
- ✓ Not Sure

- *What Changes Could Be Made to the Current Incentive Programs to Improve Employee Satisfaction? (Open-Ended)*

✓ _____

➤ *Section 5: Suggestions for Improvement*

- *What Additional Incentives or Rewards Would you Like to See Introduced in your Current Organization? (Select all that Apply)*

- ✓ Higher bonuses
- ✓ Salary increases
- ✓ Flexible working hours
- ✓ More recognition programs
- ✓ Better career advancement and opportunities
- ✓ More training and development programs

- ✓ More paid over time
- ✓ Other (Please specify) _____

Thank you for your participation!

This questionnaire assesses the incentives offered and how they influence employee satisfaction/motivation, engagement, productivity, and job retention in Cabanatuan City. The data collected can help the researchers understand which incentives are most effective and how to optimize them.

I. *Data Gathering Procedures*

The following steps will be followed to ensure systematic and efficient data collection:

➤ *Preparation of Research Instruments*

The first step is to develop and finalize the survey questionnaire and interview guide. The questionnaire will include a Likert scale, multiple-choice, and open-ended questions to assess employee satisfaction and the role of incentives. The interview guide will be prepared for semi-structured interviews with managers and focus group discussions with employees to gather qualitative insights.

J. *Validation of The Research Instruments*

Before administering the questionnaire, it will undergo a validation process. A panel of experts (e.g., professors and statisticians) will review it to ensure its clarity, relevance, and appropriateness for the study's objectives. A pilot test will be conducted with a small group of respondents to identify issues and make necessary adjustments.

K. *Distribution of Survey Questionnaires*

Once approval is granted, the survey questionnaire will be distributed to employees of the participating organizations. The distribution can be done in two ways:

- **Online Survey:** The questionnaire will be shared electronically using platforms like Google Forms or SurveyMonkey for easy access.
- **Paper-Based Survey:** Where online distribution is not feasible, printed copies of the questionnaire will be handed out to employees.

Respondents will be given clear instructions on completing the survey and the timeframe for submission (e.g., 1 to 5 days).

L. *Follow-Up and Collection of Completed Surveys*

After the initial distribution, a follow-up will be done to remind respondents to complete and submit their questionnaires.

➤ *Document Review*

Relevant organizational documents, such as incentive policy guidelines and performance reports, will be reviewed to complement the survey and interview data. This step will help verify the types of incentives offered by the organizations and evaluate how they align with the feedback provided by employees.

➤ *Data Compilation and Organization*

After all the surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions have been completed, the data will be compiled. Survey responses will be encoded into statistical software (e.g., SPSS, Excel) for quantitative analysis. The qualitative data from interviews and FGDs will be transcribed and categorized for thematic analysis.

➤ *Ethical Considerations*

Throughout the data collection process, ethical standards will be strictly adhered to. All respondents will be given informed consent, ensuring their participation is voluntary and that their identities and responses are kept confidential.

➤ *Data Analysis Technique*

Both **quantitative** and **qualitative** data will be collected. Data analysis techniques will be used to analyze the data obtained from survey questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions (FGDs).

- *Quantitative Analysis*

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize gathered data, utilizing frequencies, percentages, and means to gain insights into trends in employee satisfaction and their desire for incentives. Correlation and regression analysis will then be employed to investigate the relationships between employee satisfaction and various incentive types, helping the researchers to identify which incentives have the most significant impact on overall satisfaction of employees. Additionally, cross-tabulation will be utilized to compare satisfaction

levels across different demographic groups, such as job level or years of service, providing a deeper understanding of how these factors influence employees' perceptions of incentives and job satisfaction.

- *Qualitative Analysis*

Thematic analysis will be used to identify the recurring thread from interviews and focus group discussions offering valuable insights into how different types of incentives can impact and affect employee satisfaction. Additionally, content analysis will be used to categorized textual data to quantify standard terms and phrases related to incentives and satisfaction, providing a structured understanding of the responses. To ensure the validity of the findings and offer comprehensive view, triangulation will be employed by the researchers, where both quantitative and qualitative data will be compared. This approach will allow for a more robust analysis, confirming the consistency of the results and deepening the understanding of employee perceptions.

M. Ethical Consideration

This study ensures ethical integrity by obtaining informed consent, maintaining anonymity, safeguarding confidentiality, and encouraging voluntary participation. Approval from relevant ethics boards will also be secured to protect participants' rights and uphold research standards.

- *Informed Consent*

Participants will be fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequences.

- *Confidentiality*

All responses will be kept confidential and anonymous to protect participants' identities. Data will be stored securely and accessible only to the research team.

- *Voluntary Participation*

Participation in the study will be voluntary, ensuring employees can express their opinions without coercion.

- *Data Use*

The data collected will be used solely for research purposes and reported in aggregate form to avoid identifying individual respondents.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter focuses on the methods used to collect, present, and analyze data for the study “The Role of Incentives in Enhancing Employee Satisfaction: A Comprehensive Analysis.” It outlines the data collection process, the tools and techniques employed, and the approach to interpreting the findings. The chapter aims to clearly understand how the research objectives were addressed through systematic analysis of quantitative and qualitative data.

A. Presentation

SOP 1 Profile of the respondents (Demographic Characteristics)

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=70)	Percentage (100%)
Age		
20-29 years old	29	41.40
30-39 years old	25	35.70
40-49 years old	16	22.90
50 and above	0	0
Total	70	100.00
Gender		
Male	30	42.90
Female	40	57.10
Total	70	100.00
Position		
Entry-level	19	27.10
Mid-level	34	48.60
Senior-level	10	14.30
Managerial Level	7	100
More than 10 years	0	0
Total	70	100.00
Years of Experience:		
Less than 1 year	12	17.10
1-3 years	34	48.60
4-6 years	19	27.10
7-10 years	5	7.1
Over 10 years	0	0
Total	70	100.00
Industry Sector		
Manufacturing	5	7.14
Retailing	17	24.29
Services	20	28.57
IT/Tech	5	7.14
Education	15	21.43
Healthcare	8	11.43
Other	0	0
Total	70	100.00

➤ Section 2

Table 2: Incentive Programs in your organization

1. Does your organization offer any form of incentives?	Frequency (n=70)	Percentage (100%)
Yes	70	100.00
No	0	0
Total	70	100.00
2. If yes, what types of incentives are provided? (Select all that apply)		
Performance- based bonuses	64	25.70
Profit- sharing	17	6.80
Recognition programs	30	12.0
Flexible work hours	37	14.90
Extra Paid time- off	47	18.90
Professional development opportunities	14	5.60
Promotions or career advancement opportunities	7	2.80
Non- monetary rewards	33	13.30
Total	100.00	100.00
3. Which type of incentive motivates you the most?		
Monetary	18	25.70
Non- monetary	0	0
Both equally	52	74.30
Total	70	100.0

➤ Section 3: Effectiveness of Incentives

Table 3: 1. To what extent do incentives motivate you to perform better at work?

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
1. To what extent do incentives motivate you to perform better at work?	4.01	Highly
Grand Mean	3.12	Highly
<i>Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Extremely; 3.41–4.20 Highly –; 2.61–3.40 – Moderately - 1.81–2.60 –Slightly; 1.00–1.80 –Not at all</i>		

Table 3 The rate of the extent incentives motivates the respondents

- *Do Incentives Increase your Overall Job Satisfaction?*

Table 4: The Rate Incentives Increase the Job Satisfaction of the Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Do incentives increase your overall job satisfaction/equity and its potential benefits?	3.74	Agree
Grand Mean	3.74	Agree

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Strongly Agree 3.41–4.20 – Agree; 2.61–3.40 – Neutral - 1.81–2.60 –Disagree 1.00–1.80 – Strongly Disagree

Table 5: Percentage Rate of Respondents Satisfaction that has been Affected by Incentives

Which of the following has improved the most due to incentives?

	Frequency (n=70)	Percentage (100.00)
Job Satisfaction	21	30.0
Engagement/Commitment	13	18.60
Teamwork	15	21.40
Creativity/Innovation	4	5.70
Job Retention	17	24.30
Total	70	100.00

➤ Section 4

Table 6: Employee Engagement and Productivity

1. How often do you feel more engaged with your work when incentives are offered?

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
1. How often do you feel more engaged with your work when incentives are offered?	4.21	Always
Grand Mean		

Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Always 3.41–4.20 – Often; 2.61–3.40 – Sometimes - 1.81–2.60 –rarely 1.00–1.80 – Never

Table 7: Employee Engagement and Productivity

Do you believe that incentives have improved your work performance?

Do you believe that incentives have contributed to improving your work performance?	Frequency (n=70)	Percentage (100%)
Yes	49	70.0
No	0	0
Not Sure	21	30.0
Total	70	100.00

➤ Section 5

Table 8: Retention and Job Satisfaction

Do incentives make you more likely to stay with your current employer?

1. Do incentives make you more likely to stay with your current employer?	Frequency (n=70)	Percentage (100%)
Yes	34	48.60
No	20	28.60
Not Sure	16	22.90
Total	70	100.00

Table 9: Retention and Job Satisfaction
How satisfied are you with the incentives provided by your organization?

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
2. How satisfied are you with the incentives provided by your organization?	4.16	Satisfied
Grand Mean	4.16	Satisfied
<i>Legend: 4.21–5.00 – Very Satisfied 3.41–4.20 – Satisfied; 2.61–3.40 – Neutral - 1.81–2.60 – Dissatisfied 1.00–1.80 – Very Dissatisfied</i>		

B. Interpretation or Analysis

The data gathered by the researchers from the surveys and questionnaires they conducted on incentives and employee satisfaction provided them with valuable insights into how incentives can motivate and satisfy employees in an organization. Below is a detailed analysis of the findings based on the above-presented data:

➤ Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

• Age Distribution

The age distribution of respondents shows different ranges of employees, with most of them falling within the ages of 20-29 years old and 30-39 years of age. This is an important insight because it suggests that incentives must be tailored depending on the age and stage of employees' careers. Younger employees (20-29 years old) prioritize monetary incentives (performance-based bonuses, extra paid time off), while older employees (30-39, 40-49 years old) value stability, work-life balance, and recognition.

• Gender Distribution

The gender distribution is balanced, which implies that incentive programs should always cater to both male and female employees equally. Any discrepancy in how employees of different genders respond to incentives could suggest areas for further improvement in the organization's incentive design.

• Position in the Company

The position in the company stated a significant difference in satisfaction with what type of incentives they prefer.

• Length of Experience

Employees who have been with the organization for 1-3 years make up a significant portion of the respondents in the survey, reflecting the importance of employee retention. Incentives that promote long-term sustainability, such as performance-based bonuses, recognition programs, promotions, or career advancement opportunities, are relevant for this group.

➤ Types of Incentive Programs

• Monetary Incentives

Monetary rewards (e.g., performance-based bonuses, extra paid time off, profit-sharing, salary increases) were the most reported incentives, with 68.20% of employees receiving this form of incentives/ rewards in the past years. This supports the research study that salaries and bonuses are critical motivators for employees. Nonetheless, the effect of financial rewards on long-term contentment can differ. While they can enhance immediate motivation, they might not lead to lasting satisfaction unless other internal incentives like recognition or opportunities for advancement accompany them.

• Non-Monetary Incentives

Recognition programs, flexible work hours, professional development opportunities, promotions, and career advancement opportunities are incentives that most respondents also receive. However, it less affects employees' job satisfaction compared to monetary incentives. Aside from monetary incentives, recognition, and career development are the most mentioned, showing that employees value personal growth and love to be recognized. This suggests that organizations should not focus solely on monetary rewards but also give importance to their employees by recognizing them as it fosters a sense of accomplishment and belongingness.

➤ Effectiveness of Incentives

With a grand mean of 3.12 (Highly) motivated by the incentives they received. This suggests that incentives effectively drive employees' job satisfaction and performance. Monetary incentives tend to provide short-term contentment or motivation. At the same time, recognition and career development opportunities will likely contribute to long-term motivation for employees to perform well in their jobs.

The data gathered suggests that incentives, both monetary and non-monetary, contribute directly to the higher motivation rate and job performance of employees. Employees who are given monetary incentives and recognition are more engaged, motivated, and satisfied with their work.

➤ *Open- Ended Responses*

• *Desired Incentives for the Future*

Many respondents expressed a desire for increased career advancement opportunities. This suggests that a growing portion of the employees in Cabanatuan City prioritize self-value and career opportunities over purely financial incentives.

• *Suggestions for Improvements*

Many of the respondents suggested that customizing incentives based on individual needs and preferences is more likely to be effective in motivating and satisfying employees in their current jobs.

C. *Interpretation*

The survey/ questionnaire shows that monetary incentives (such as salary increases, performance-based bonuses, and extra paid time-off) are the most provided rewards, with 68.20 % of employees receiving them from their current organization. While monetary incentives are vital in meeting the basic financial needs of the employees and giving them short-term motivation, they alone are insufficient in satisfying and motivating employees to perform well in their jobs. This study highlights that financial rewards are essential but should go well with non-monetary incentives such as recognition, career development opportunities, and flexible work arrangements.

Employees who received recognition (12%), career advancement/development opportunities (8.40 %), and flexible work arrangements (14.90%) expressed greater long-term satisfaction. This suggests that employees nowadays value the feeling of being appreciated and having opportunities for personal growth.

With a grand mean of 3.12 (highly motivated), employees who receive monetary and non-monetary incentives express more eagerness to work and are more satisfied with their jobs. A grand mean of 3.74 (100%) agreed that incentives play a vital role in the satisfaction and motivation of employees in their work. This highlights that rewards energize employees, and they are more likely to perform better when adequately incentivized. It also shows the strong relationship between incentives and job satisfaction, where (100%) of the respondents depict that effective incentive programs can enhance employees' productivity, engagement, and commitment to attaining their company's organizational goals.

This survey shows that 48.60% of the total respondents are more likely to stay with their current employer and are satisfied with the incentive programs they received. A total of 20, or (28.60%) of the total number of respondents, answered that they are not happy with their company's current incentive programs and are not willing to stay long with them, and 16, or (22.80%) are not sure if they are willing to stay with their current employer because of the incentives that they received.

With a grand mean of 4.16 (very satisfied), employees are very satisfied with the overall incentives provided by their organization, indicating that incentives play a crucial role in boosting job satisfaction and motivation in most employees in Cabanatuan City.

CHAPTER FOUR

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the discussion, conclusions, and recommendations based on the study's findings, "The Role of Incentives in Enhancing Employee Satisfaction: A Comprehensive Analysis." It interprets the results from the previous chapter, connects them to the research objectives, and highlights their implications. Additionally, it provides actionable recommendations for improving employee satisfaction through effective incentive programs and identifies areas for future research.

A. Summary

Employee satisfaction and motivation are key factors in identifying the overall performance of an organization that influences the productivity, retention, and overall morale of a workforce. This study highlights the effectiveness of incentives in enhancing the satisfaction of employees using strategic rewards programs such as monetary (e.g., salary increases, performance-based bonuses, profit-sharing, and extra paid time off) and non-monetary (recognition, flexible work hours, professional development, and career opportunities).

This study explored the impact of both types of incentive programs (monetary and non-monetary) on employee satisfaction and identified how organizations can design effective incentive programs that are more tailored to their employees' needs.

Employees generally expressed their job satisfaction with the increased salaries, performance-based bonuses, and extra paid time off, but the effectiveness of these incentives can vary. Some of the interviewed employees reported that salary increases and bonuses motivated them to perform better, while others feel that sometimes, these bonuses are not aligned with their performance.

Non-monetary incentives (e.g., recognition, professional and career development, flexible working hours) are also important factors affecting employee satisfaction. Employees who receive recognition and acknowledgment for their work are more motivated and engaged. Additionally, non-monetary incentives like professional and career development are highly valued, especially by younger employees ages 20- 39.

Employee preferences for incentive programs vary depending on demographic factors such as age, sex, department/ industry, job level or positions, and years of service with the company. For instance, younger employees prefer career growth opportunities and flexible work arrangements, while older employees prioritize financial security.

The outcome of the conducted survey/ questionnaire highlights that employees value both monetary and non-monetary incentives. While financial incentives remain a significant factor in job satisfaction, non-monetary rewards also play an important role in enhancing the overall satisfaction of employees, especially those from Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija.

B. Conclusions

This comprehensive analysis emphasized the importance of monetary and non-monetary incentives in managing employee satisfaction and engagement. The findings identified that while financial incentives remain the best in attaining employee satisfaction, non-monetary incentives such as recognition, career and professional opportunities, and flexible work-life balance are equally important in fostering a motivated, satisfied, engaged, and committed workforce.

Employee preferences for the type of incentives they receive vary depending on demographic factors such as age, sex, job level position, and tenure. The study stated the importance of tailoring incentive programs to suit the specific needs of different employee segments to maximize their effectiveness.

Performance-based bonuses, salary increases, and extra paid time off incentives play important roles in motivating employees and satisfying their financial needs. However, employee satisfaction does not solely rely on receiving monetary incentives, as these incentives only give them short-term satisfaction.

Non-financial rewards or incentives such as recognition, career and professional development, and flexible work arrangements are increasingly important to employees. Many employees, particularly younger ones, are more motivated when given recognition and acknowledgment and a supportive work culture rather than just receiving financial rewards. Employees tend to be more engaged, loyal, and productive when these needs are met.

The most effective incentive reward systems use a combination of monetary and non-monetary incentives to address the diverse needs of their employees. The survey stated that employees appreciate competitive salaries and bonuses but are also motivated when working. They are given proper recognition, and career and professional advancement are given to them. Using a balanced financial and non-financial rewards system leads to higher employee satisfaction.

C. Recommendations

The researchers of the study recommend a regular review and evaluation of the organization's incentive system to determine if the rewards programs currently used by the organization are still effective and ensure that they remain aligned with the organization's expectations, market trends, and overall goals.

The researchers recommend promoting Non- Monetary Incentives in addition to the existing and commonly used financial rewards as the result of the survey indicated and emphasized that employees are more motivated, satisfied, and engaged in their work if a combination of monetary and non-monetary rewards are given to them.

The study also recommends that incentive programs be customized based on the diverse needs of the different employee groups in the organization. In this advanced world, a one-size-fits-all approach is less effective than personalized or customized programs catering to individual preferences and departmental requirements.

This research concluded that a well-balanced use of monetary incentives (e.g., salary increases, bonuses, extra paid time off) and non-monetary incentives (e.g., recognition, flexible work arrangements, career and professional growth) are more likely to develop motivated, satisfied, and high-performing employees. These strategies will improve organizational outcomes, including higher retention rates, increased job productivity, and a more positive workplace culture.

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APPENDICES

A. Correspondence

November 4, 2024

To: **THE BRANCH HEAD**
BDO Unibank Inc, Paco- Roman Branch
Paco Roman St., Cabanatuan City
Nueva Ecija

Dear Sir/Ma'am:

Greetings of peace and prosperity!

We are a Master of Arts in Business Administration student at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, and we are conducting a research study titled **THE ROLE OF INCENTIVES IN ENHANCING EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS**.

In line with this, we are humbly soliciting your support by allowing us to conduct a short survey via Google Forms and interview some of your office personnel who are regularly receiving incentives. We have attached a copy of the questionnaire for data collection and sample interview questions regarding the incentive or reward system provided by your organization to the Google form.

Rest assured that the requested data will be strictly for research purposes only and will be kept confidential.

Thank you very much in advance, and we are looking forward to this request for your most favorable response.

Very sincerely yours,

GLADYS ANNE E. CADAY

MELVIEROSE T. CARDONA
Researchers

Noted by:

DR. NOEL B. AGUSTIN, PH.D.
Subject Professor (Organizational Behavior)

Received by:

November 4, 2024

To: **THE MANAGER**
Joey's Restaurant Cafe
General Luna St., Cabanatuan City
Nueva Ecija

Dear Sir/Ma'am:

Greetings of peace and prosperity!

We are a Master of Arts in Business Administration student at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, and we are conducting a research study titled THE ROLE OF INCENTIVES IN ENHANCING EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS.

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GLADYS ANNE E. CADAY

MELVIEROSE T. CARDONA
Researchers

Noted by:

DR. NOEL B. AGUSTIN, PH.D.
Subject Professor (Organizational Behavior)

Received by:

November 4, 2024

To: **THE BRANCH HEAD**
SSS Cabanatuan
N.E Pacific Mall., Cabanatuan City
Nueva Ecija

Dear Sir/Ma'am:

Greetings of peace and prosperity!

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GLADYS ANNE E. CADAY

MELVIEROSE T. CARDONA
Researchers

Noted by:

DR. NOEL B. AGUSTIN, PH.D.
Subject Professor (Organizational Behavior)

Received by:

November 4, 2024

To: **THE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGER**
SM City Cabanatuan
Maharlika Highway, Cabanatuan City
Nueva Ecija

Dear Sir/Ma'am:

Greetings of peace and prosperity!

We are a Master of Arts in Business Administration student at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, and we are conducting a research study titled THE ROLE OF INCENTIVES IN ENHANCING EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS.

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MELVIEROSE T. CARDONA
Researchers

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Subject Professor (Organizational Behavior)

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November 4, 2024

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Thank you very much in advance, and we are looking forward to this request for your most favorable response.

Very sincerely yours,

GLADYS ANNE E. CADAY

MELVIEROSE T. CARDONA
Researchers

Noted by:

DR. NOEL B. AGUSTIN, PH.D.
Subject Professor (Organizational Behavior)

Received by:

B. Data Gathering Instruments

D. Questionnaire: Role and Impact of Incentives on Employee Satisfaction in Cabanatuan City This questionnaire is designed to assess the role and impact of incentives on employee satisfaction in the various sectors of Cabanatuan City. Your honest responses will greatly help and contribute to the success of this study. All information provided will be handle with utmost discretion and will be kept confidential and will only be use for the purpose of the study.

E. Instructions: Please put a check mark on your chosen answer.

➤ Section I: Demographic Information

- *Age*

- ✓ 18-25
- ✓ 26-35
- ✓ 36-45
- ✓ 46-55
- ✓ 56 and above

- *Gender:*

- ✓ Male
- ✓ Female
- ✓ Other

- *Job Position:*

- ✓ Entry-level
- ✓ Mid-level
- ✓ Senior-level
- ✓ Managerial Level
- ✓ Executive

- *Years of Experience in the Organization:*

- ✓ Less than 1 year
- ✓ 1-3 years
- ✓ 4-6 years
- ✓ 7-10 years
- ✓ More than 10 years

- *Industry Sector:*

- ✓ Manufacturing
 - ✓ Retailing
 - ✓ Services
 - ✓ IT/Tech
 - ✓ Education
 - ✓ Healthcare
 - ✓ Other (Please specify)
 - ✓ _____
-

➤ *Section 2: Incentive Programs in your organization*

• *Does your Organization offer Any Form of Incentives?*

- ✓ Yes
- ✓ No
- ✓ If yes, what types of incentives are provided? (Select all that apply)
- ✓ Performance-based bonuses
- ✓ Profit- sharing
- ✓ Recognition programs (Employee of the Month, etc.)
- ✓ Flexible work hours
- ✓ Extra Paid time- off
- ✓ Professional development opportunities (training, workshops, etc.)
- ✓ Promotions or career advancement opportunities
- ✓ Non-monetary rewards (gifts, vouchers, etc.)
- ✓ Other (please specify if possible)
- ✓ _____

• *Which type of Incentive Motivates you the Most?*

- ✓ Monetary (bonuses, salary increases)
- ✓ Non-monetary (recognition, career growth opportunities, etc.)
- ✓ Both equally

➤ *Section 3. Perceived Impact of Incentives on Job Satisfaction*

• *To What Extent do Monetary Incentives Influence your Overall Job Satisfaction?*

- ✓ 1: No Influence
- ✓ 2: Little Influence
- ✓ 3: Some Influence
- ✓ 4: Moderate Influence
- ✓ 5: Strong Influence

• *To What Extent Do Non-Monetary Incentives Influence Your Overall Job Satisfaction?*

- ✓ 1: No Influence
- ✓ 2: Little Influence
- ✓ 3: Some Influence
- ✓ 4: Moderate Influence
- ✓ 5: Strong Influence

• *Which Type of Incentive do you Value More in your Current Role?*

- ✓ Monetary Incentives
- ✓ Non- monetary Incentives
- ✓ Both Equally

• *How important are incentives in keeping you motivated and satisfied in your job?*

- ✓ 1: Not Important
- ✓ 2: Slightly Important
- ✓ 3: Moderately Important
- ✓ 4: Important
- ✓ 5: Very Important

- *What is the most Effective Incentive you have Received? (Open-ended)*

✓ _____

➤ *Section 4: Job Satisfaction*

- *Overall, how satisfied are you with your job?*

- ✓ 1: Very Dissatisfied
- ✓ 2: Dissatisfied
- ✓ 3: Neutral
- ✓ 4: Satisfied
- ✓ 5: Very Satisfied

- *Do you believe that the incentives provided by your organization align with your personal and professional goals?*

- ✓ Yes
- ✓ No
- ✓ Not Sure

- *What changes could be made to the current incentive programs to improve employee satisfaction? (Open-ended)*

✓ _____

➤ *Section 5: Suggestions for Improvement*

- *What additional incentives or rewards would you like to see introduced in your current organization? (Select all that apply)*

- ✓ Higher bonuses
- ✓ Salary increases
- ✓ Flexible working hours
- ✓ More recognition programs
- ✓ Better career advancement and opportunities
- ✓ More training and development programs
- ✓ More paid over time
- ✓ Other (Please specify) _____

Thank you for your participation!

This questionnaire assesses the incentives offered and how they influence employee satisfaction/motivation, engagement, productivity, and job retention in Cabanatuan City. The data collected can help the researchers understand which incentives are most effective and how to optimize them.

C. Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted by the researchers through google forms to assess the effectiveness of the survey and the clarity of questions related to the role of incentives in enhancing employee satisfaction. The pilot involved 21 employees from various sectors, including manufacturing, services (23.8%), information technology (9.5%), retail (19%), healthcare (4.8 %), education (14.3 %) and others (28.6%). These participants were selected to reflect a diverse range of job levels, including entry-level, mid-level, and senior-level employees.

The results from the pilot study indicated that most of the participants selected have been receiving incentives, with a response rate of 90.5 % and only 9.5 % of them are not receiving incentives from their organization. However, some areas required clarification. Specifically, the questions related to non-monetary incentives, such as career development and recognition, were not fully understood by a few respondents, who suggested that these concepts needed clearer definitions. In response, the survey was revised to provide more explicit descriptions of non-monetary incentives to avoid confusion in the main study.

Regarding the core focus of the study, employee satisfaction with current incentive programs was generally positive, with 33.3 % of participants reporting that monetary incentives, such as bonuses and raises, significantly impacted their job satisfaction. However, there was a big also notable interest of the respondents on incentives that offers both monetary and non-monetary rewards, were most of the respondents 66.7 % emphasized the need also for professional growth opportunities and work-life balance in their job satisfaction.

Furthermore, feedback from the qualitative section revealed that employees felt incentivized programs should be tailored to individual needs and career stages. For instance, younger employees expressed a preference for skill development opportunities, while more senior employees valued recognition and autonomy.

The pilot study also revealed a minor issue with the wording of the Likert scale items, where some participants were unsure whether to rate certain statements on a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Very Important). As a result, the scale was modified for the main study to include clearer anchors for the responses.

In conclusion, the pilot study provided valuable insights into the types of incentives that influence employee satisfaction and highlighted areas for improvement in survey design. Based on these findings, adjustments were made to the final survey to ensure clarity, accuracy, and relevance to the broader employee population. The successful completion of the pilot study validated the research approach, allowing for a smoother transition into the full-scale study.